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THE FLUID COMPETENCE LEVEL-ORIENTED ADVANCED PROJECT LABORATORY (FCLPL) IN PHYSICS

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ABSTRACT

The fluid competence level-oriented project laboratory in the advanced practical courses of our Bachelor and Master programs of physics with up to 50 students per semester enables students to gradually grow into self-developed experiments. The students formulate a project idea and while conducting their project the students continuously proceed with the project development in close contact to their supervisors. If the students develop convincing ideas they can continue with projects XL or XXL and expand their initial ideas. The basic experiments of the practical course which had originally been assigned to the students at the beginning of the semester are gradually omitted and are replaced by a project XL or XXL. The students improve their initial project idea and write proposals and documentation. Research, experiments and documentation alternate successively and thus enable the ongoing improvement of the projects and the constant documentation and evaluation. The practical courses profit from a steady refinement as new experiments are continuously developed by the students themselves.

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1 INTRODUCTION

An extremely important question which needs to be addressed by universities is how to educate young students enabling them to solve future large-scale problems. We believe that a competence level-oriented advanced student laboratory contributes to the development of such skills and we developed such a teaching format for the advanced practical courses in the Bachelor of Physics and the Master of Physics at Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg. The competence levels of Bloom's taxonomy [1] are achieved in a consecutive and hierarchical sequence. The creation of something new requires remembering, understanding and critical reflection of the content of previous teaching levels to set the stage for further progress. Each level requires exercise and self-reflection combined with the phantasy to drive creative processes. Knowledge and competence emerge from a steady development process, as psychological studies [2, 3] and error research [4, 5] show.

Research-based project courses provide a chance to reshape teaching, endowing students with the capability to master problems occurring later in their professional life [6, 7]. These problem-related competences need higher priority in universities. For this purpose, new didactic strategies have to be developed. This applies both to theoretical topics [8, 9, 10] and experimental modules (e.g. practical courses) [9, 11] and is strongly linked to project-based and research-based learning [11-16].

Project work is not necessarily a sure-fire success at universities. A big problem is a certain fear among the students to devote themselves to the challenges of a project. The basic teaching modules are often found important enough to deserve all attention. This means that often only a few students volunteer for a project. Integrating mandatory projects with high complexity into the curricula may not do justice to the heterogeneity and diversity of the students. That is why we suggest a learning format in which the students can grow individually with their projects.

The evaluations of our students' interests show [11,14,15] that they want motivation and orientation in their studies in two ways. On the one hand, students want to develop specialist skills and decide on their master's thesis or doctorate. On the other hand, many students are also interested in the acquisition of interdisciplinary skills to deal with complex problems, especially questions of sustainable development. They want to see meaning in their work. Project teaching is rated as helpful for both.

The projects in the fluid competence level-oriented advanced project laboratory in physics (FCLPL) are deliberately not limited to physics alone. We motivate students to think in an interdisciplinary manner and also to go beyond the questions of classical physics. Particularly good students can develop their potential freely by expanding their projects successively.

2 CONCEPT AND METHODS OF THE FLUID COMPETENCE LEVEL-ORIENTED ADVANCED PROJECT LABORATORY IN PHYSICS (FCLPL)

2.1 Formal requirements

The advanced practical courses in the Bachelor of Physics and the practical courses in the Master of Physics measure 6 credit points (i.e. 180 hours of student engagement) for the Bachelor and 10 credit points (i.e. 300 hours) for Master's laboratory course. The full Bachelor practical course has to be passed by about 50 students in the Bachelor of Physics, Bachelor in Medical Physics and Teaching degree in the summer semester, the Master course by generally less than 20 students of physics only during the winter term. So especially in summer the students are composed heterogeneously. Usually students conduct 5 basic experiments in groups of two students. The idea of the FCLPL is to implement projects into both practical courses (Bachelor and Master) without changing the structure of both modules.

In the FCLPL the students have to formulate an obligatory project idea at the beginning of the semester. This idea is discussed together with the teachers and the students can develop it to a project experiment. In the Bachelor program such project experiments are facultative and can be executed voluntarily while at least one project experiment is mandatory for the practical physics course in the Master's program that can be expanded to a project XL or project XXL.

In such case the basic experiments of the internship assigned at the beginning of the semester are gradually omitted as long as the project grows to XL or XXL (See Fig. 1). Therefore the teaching load for both, students and the involved staff, stays constant. The students finally carry out a total of 2-5 advanced experiments in the practical courses of both, Bachelor and Master of Physics, as gradual and fluid access to research-based learning can be exploited to varying degrees.

Fig. 1. Project experiments, projects XL and projects XXL in the practical courses.

2.2 Implementation of a project, project XL or project XXL

At the beginning we suggest possible research topics suitable for projects XL or XXL, but with an open outcome, since the projects are refined and redesigned in an evolutionary process. Publications of current research topics are discussed so that the students are motivated to recognize the current state of science but already try to think beyond – not necessarily with the focus on a deep scientific approach but in a broader sense of how to transfer recent scientific findings to their project.

Once a topic has been chosen, the students formulate a hypothesis and a proposal for research, a realistic goal and concrete research methods. The students perform the necessary literature research and present their ideas to the supervisors who agree with the students' suggestions. The important construction of the FCLPL is done in such way that the module can run as initially planned without a change of the lab structure allowing student projects to be implemented on the fly, while the practical course is running. This is achieved as outlined in Fig. 1.

Five standard experiments are suggested at the beginning of the semester. For the experiment which is suggested to be substituted by a project, an extended research question, an extension of the methodological approach and a possible further experimental approach may be proposed. The feasibility of the project proposal is discussed with the supervisors during the lab course which takes place weekly for 5 SWS (teaching hours).

If the students succeed in carrying out the proposed part of the project, they apply with new ideas for the continuation of the project on an enlarged project experiment XL, which can expand the ongoing research or touch a new question. It replaces a (second) standard experiment if the recent results of the project and the proposal for the continuation of the project experiment XL are convincing. The decision to continue the project is discussed between students and advisors. If the XL project is also successful and a concept for an XXL project is presented, it can be expanded to replace another (third) standard experiment. If the students lose interest in their project work, they can always return to the initially suggested basic experiments that were assigned to them at the beginning of the semester.

The FCLPL is conceptually a hybrid module that combines a physical project module with a normal experimental course in the practical courses.

An XL or XXL project attempt is not only submitted as an ordinary protocol but preferably concluded with a seminar talk, a poster presentation or even a small publication or as a blog article in the internet, ideally in combination with public events such as the Long Night of the Sciences. For that purpose the practical course combines 5 hours of laboratory work per week (5 SWS) with 1 hour weekly seminar per week (1 SWS). It involves 6 teachers with a workload of 4 – 8 SWS each for 50 students in the same way as the practical course in the standard format (without projects). All experiments are conducted within the rooms of the practical courses on the setups available there however the extension of single experiments can also be

performed in collaboration with and within the rooms of the working groups of the University.

2.3 Achieved Competences in the FCLPL, seminar and poster presentation

In detail, the following interdisciplinary skills are taught to the students in the FCLPL:

- Working out the theoretical and experimental basics of self-selected questions (literature and information research)
- Acquiring performative skills by imitating a real problem without a fixed solution (in the sense of research-based learning)
- Planning, implementation, evaluation and documentation of a scientific project
- Understanding failure as a learning path
- Assessment and critical reflection on one's own work
- Critical error analysis as a basis for innovative further development and improvement
- Basics of multimedia documentation
- Seminar Talks
- Scientific writing and publication
- Poster Presentations
- Writing of project proposals
- Convincing argumentation and discussion of your own results in front of a group

The work in the FCLPLP is carried out in close contact between lecturers and students, who conduct regular meetings or video conferences. This ensures that the students' problems are communicated promptly and solved by the advisors during ongoing operations (ambulatory assessment).

The FCLPL offers students and teachers more flexibility. Seminars, poster presentations, meetings and the implementation of the experiments are supported online and the time for experiments can be freely planned in agreement between teachers and students. The presence during the internship is concentrated on a limited number of intensive days (typically 1-2 days per experiment and/or project level).

2.4 Elements of digital teaching

Digitalization plays a major role in communication and science including the acquisition of and the search for knowledge. It enables a quick literature search, the administration and sharing of information and the collaborative evaluation and documentation including the recording of actions and progress. Secondly, digitalization can support self-directed learning as it makes students independent from the university as extensively elaborated during the Covid-19 lockdowns. Thirdly, digitalization offers transfer possibilities between disciplines and institutions as well as towards the public when research outcome and learning content is shared in social networks, on blogs or via videos. It is useful to record the students' current experiences and behavior in a timely manner, and, if necessary, to intervene in a controlling manner

(ambulatory assessment) [17,18]. Such recording can be achieved simply by establishing a digital laboratory documentation system (lab book) or project planning tools (we used Trello®, GitLab® and Slack®) that allow for collaborative work, documentation, tracking and the steady review of the outcomes.

We offer the students a digital environment, in which they can transform their already acquired knowledge from different disciplines as well as their own digital skills, habits and ideas for the application of digital tools into a concrete project.

2.5 Example projects and their integration into the general syllabus

To give an example project that was extended to a project XXL we want to refer to “SEM and EBIC”, where the students had initially proposed the combined scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with simultaneous measurement of electron beam induced current (EBIC). The project took place in winter 2020/21 (See Fig. 2) and the students developed both, experimental approach and technical implementation of EBIC microscopy into a standard SEM and the theory to evaluate EBIC images. The finally resulting project XXL was of such interest that the students' efforts were used to completely overwork the standard experiment as it is usually offered in both Bachelor advanced practical courses and Masters' practical courses. In such way the students not only developed their own project but they contributed to the steady development of the whole teaching module.

It is foreseen that this approach will therefore be continued in such way that good projects are implemented into the practical courses as regular experiments.

Further example experiments that have already been conducted and contributed to the development of the practical courses are

- Physics of the photosynthesis – time resolved fluorescence spectroscopy to describe energy and electron transfer processes in living photosynthetic cells (project XL)
- Optical and electronic properties of semiconductors investigated by spectroscopy, temperature dependent conductivity, magnetoresistance and Hall-effekt (Project XL)
- Temperature- und frequency dependent permittivity of water and polymers during phase transitions (Project XL)
- Combined scanning electron microscopy and electron beam induced current (Project XXL)
- Characterization of a novel setup for the tension dependent viscosity of complex fluids (Project XXL)
- Establishment of an x-ray diffraction setup for structure analysis by Laue-spectroscopy (Project XL)
- Photovoltaics and Solar Cells (Project XL)
- Environmental radioactivity, Gamma-spectroscopy and self built Geiger-Müller counters (Project XXL)

Fig. 2. Elements of the project “SEM and EBIC”

3 POSSIBLE TRANSFER TO OTHER CURRICULA

The FCLPL is now implemented into the advanced physics laboratory of the Bachelor and the practical courses of the Masters of physics at Martin-Luther-Universität Halle-Wittenberg. It is a tool for a steady development of the curricula and it is a compulsory module for the Bachelor and Master in Physics and Medical Physics as well as for ongoing physics teachers.

The FCLPL is therefore already designed as part of 4 different modules for the different subjects. From next year also the students of Physics and Digital Technology and students of “Physics Plus” will participate in the FCLPL.

The idea of a project experiment, into which the students can grow, can be transferred to all curricula without principal restrictions. The idea takes into account the concerns that students could be overwhelmed with projects and at the same time targets the need that especially very good students should be challenged by particularly extensive projects. The heterogeneity of the educational access is thus taken into account through a fluid adaptation to the learning behavior and the motivation of individual students.

4 EVALUATION RESULTS AND QUALITY OF SEMINAR TALKS AND POSTER PRESENTATIONS

The FCLPL was evaluated several times by the central evaluation of the MLU with special attention to the project experiments. Further interviews with the students of the physics department gave insights into the students' interests and wishes.

In this way, it was possible to improve the course during ongoing operations and thus make conceptual risks visible early enough to react. For example the Masters students rated the project experiments very good and turned out to be highly motivated to undergo projects. The Bachelor students, possibly overwhelmed by large workload, were not easily activated to participate in projects. Therefore the suggested structure with voluntary projects in the Bachelor and mandatory projects in the Master was developed.

The general aspect to be able to conduct project experiments was judged very positively during the evaluations and the students declared themselves as highly comfortable with the structure of the modules.

As supervisors we judged the quality of the seminar talks and poster presentations that were given on the project experiments. The projects were found to have highest quality with all marks ranging between 1.0 and 2.0 with an average of 1.3.

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